

INTERVENTION OF TECHNOLOGY TO TEACH ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

Technology is considered as an important factor in teaching English language in today's technological era. Therefore, the main purpose of this research is to identify the role of technology integration in teaching English as a foreign language. For this purpose, the descriptive content analysis is used in the research. The result of the research depicts that the intervention of technology in EFL context is beneficial both for teachers and students this is due to the fact that it makes easier for teachers to conduct a lesson in interactive and innovative way while students find it interesting and informative.

Introduction. The 21st century provides a huge amount of technologies to use in different ways. Familiar with the concept of using modern technology is not limited to the use of modern appliances and equipment, but can also introduce innovative teaching systems and methods to promote faster and more comprehensive learning processes. According to popular teaching theories, students can better acquire and hone their language knowledge and skills when using the learning potential of technology.

According to Becker, computers are regarded as an important instructional instrument in language classes in which teachers have convenient access, are sufficiently prepared, and have some freedom in the curriculum[1].

According to Pourhosein Gilakjani, the use of technologies has the great potential to change the existing language teaching methods. The use of technology in English teaching consolidates a comprehensive view of modern means systems and connections with other components, benefiting students by achieving desired results [4, p.262-267].

Hennesy stated the use of technology (ICT) acts very well in motivating the teachers and also the learners to work for the new ways. The researcher understood that as learners become more autonomous, teachers feel that they should urge and support their learners to act and think independently [3, p.155-192].

Foreign language teachers have a specific niche: Their job is to teach students a whole new language, including the nuanced rules of grammar and cultural norms. Technology offers foreign language teachers a chance to supplement their instruction by:

Making learning visible: Technology can bring another culture into the classroom. Using technology tools that connect to foreign lands and display how others live allows students to see and experience language in a whole new way.

Differentiating: Not all students are the same. Each one has different strengths and needs. Technology tools give teachers additional resources to reach all learners.

Engaging students: Technology these days is often interactive, allowing users a chance to be engaged in learning experiences. You can't do that with a book!

Applying language: With language acquisition, you either use it or lose it. Technology gives students many opportunities to use their broadening language skills in real-world applications.

When technologies are being integrated into our teaching and learning process, our students are becoming to be more interested in the subjects they are studying [5, p.1773-1785]. Technology provides different opportunities to change the learning process becoming more fun, well different and enjoyable in terms of teaching same things in new ways. For instance, delivering teaching through gamification, taking students on virtual field trips and using other online learning resources. What is more, technology are also can be able to encourage a much way more active participation in the learning process which certainly can be hard to achieve through the traditional teaching & learning environment. The learners who are involved and being interested in the things that they are studying, are absolutely expected to have a more better knowledge retention.

Computers, tablets and e-readers can all be instrumental in learning English, offering interactive and motivating activities for students of all ages. The following are ways that EFL teachers can use technology to teach English in a way that will make lessons more engaging and appealing:

Film and Video. Using short and feature-length videos is an engaging way to work on skills like vocabulary and comprehension. Videos help to expose students to the use of natural English. Young children really enjoy short cartoons and animated movies, and older students can learn about current events through news broadcasts.

Apps. Learning English can be very difficult and frustrating at times. Apps on iPads and tablets are great ways for students to practice English and have fun while doing it. For practicing grammar rules, apps like Grammar Up allow students to test their knowledge on specific topics (verbs, prepositions, etc.). The app also keeps track of students' progress and allows them to skip questions by shaking the tablet.

Podcasts. Students can listen to podcasts to improve their comprehension. They can also create podcasts to practice their English speaking abilities. A free download of iTunes gives teachers access to hundreds of free podcasts on a range of topics. There are multiple podcasts tailored specifically for English language learners. Teachers can also have students create podcasts to give them opportunities to practice their speaking skills. With just a microphone and a computer, students can create reports and presentations. Video podcasts are an attractive option for students, and some classes even have their own YouTube channel.

By using these technologies both the teachers and the students can develop so many skills during their teaching and learning process. Students can be able to gain the

skills they will need to be successful in the future. Modern learning is about collaborating with others, solving complex problems, critical thinking, developing different forms of communication and leadership skills, and improving motivation and productivity.

Conclusion. The technology provides a very big chances for making the learning activities becoming way more effective for everyone with their own different needs. Students can learn at their own speed, review difficult concepts or skip ahead if they need to. Furthermore, students can be able to practice the collaboration skills by getting themselves being involved in some different kind of online activities over the internet and technology. Teachers can be able and may use different apps or trusted online resources to enhance the traditional ways of teaching and to keep students more engaged. Virtual lesson plans, grading software and online assessments can help teachers save a lot time. This valuable time can be used for working with students who are struggling. What is more, having virtual learning environments enhances collaboration and knowledge sharing between teachers.

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